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Research Article

**PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDY OF HERB “PLECTRANTHUS
AMBOINICUS” AND TO FORMULATE A “MOSQUITO
INCENCE” AND ITS HERBAL STANDARDIZATION****Bhagyalekshmi B^{*1}, Gopika Radhakrishnan^{*2}, Grace S Shaji^{*3}, Harikrishna S M^{*4},
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Abstract:

The present study focuses on the pharmacognostical evaluation of Plectranthus amboinicus (commonly known as Indian borage) and the formulation of a herbal mosquito incense utilizing its bioactive properties. Plectranthus amboinicus is a well-known medicinal herb valued for its antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and insect-repellent properties. A detailed pharmacognostical analysis, including macroscopic, microscopic, physicochemical, and phytochemical evaluations, was conducted to establish its botanical identity and quality standards. The bioactive compounds, particularly essential oils such as thymol and carvacrol, were identified and quantified using standard analytical techniques. These compounds were leveraged to formulate a mosquito-repellent incense, combining Plectranthus amboinicus with other synergistic herbal components. The results indicate that Plectranthus amboinicus serves as an effective, sustainable, and natural alternative for mosquito control, offering potential benefits in reducing vector-borne diseases while minimizing the environmental and health hazards associated with chemical repellents. This study establishes a scientific foundation for the herb's usage in traditional medicine and its application in innovative mosquito-repellent products.

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PLANT INTRODUCTION:**The Genus *Amboinicus***

The name "*amboinicus*" alludes to the fertile mountainous island of Ambon in Indonesia's Maluku Islands. The plant spread throughout the East Indies, Africa, and Latin America, where it became known as 'oregano de la Hoja Ancha'. Cuban oregano grows naturally in Indonesian and Malaysian rainforests. This succulent plant, native to tropical Africa and Asia, is recognized by its thick, aromatic leaves, which are widely used in culinary applications, particularly in Indian and Southeast Asian cuisines⁽⁷⁾. The leaves have a distinct oregano flavour and are valued for its therapeutic characteristics, which include anti-inflammatory and antibacterial activity. They have historically been used to treat digestive and respiratory conditions. The plant is a common choice for home gardens and potted herbs since it grows well in soil that drains well and requires lots of sunlight.⁽⁸⁾

***Plectranthus amboinicus* Lour.**

One well-known species in the Lamiaceae family is *Plectranthus amboinicus*. These therapeutic herbs are widely distributed over India and are frequently used in traditional medicine. Additionally, it can treat epilepsy, pneumonia, and the flu. Using phytochemical analysis, flavanoids such as apigenin, luteolin, and salvigenin are found. With thick, meaty leaves and a stem, this perennial aromatic plant reaches a height of 30 to 90 cm.⁽⁹⁾ The leaves of this succulent herb have a unique smell and are well-branched. This plant is grown in gardens and is common throughout India. This plant's leaves can cover offensive odours and improve the flavor of meats and seafood. In Asian homes, karpuravalli plants—also called *Coleus aromaticus*—are frequently used. Around the world, researchers are currently examining the potential of antioxidant, flavourful and antimicrobial properties.⁽¹⁰⁾

Fig 1: *Plectranthus amboinicus* plant**Synonyms of *Plectranthus amboinicus* Lour.**

- *Coleus amboinicus* Lour
- *Coleus aromaticus* Benth.
- *Majana amboinica* (Lour.) Kuntze
- *Majana carnosus* (Hassk.) Kuntze⁽¹¹⁾

Vernacular names of *Plectranthus amboinicus* Lour.

- Kannada: Dodda pathre, dodda pathre soppu
- Hindi : Patta ajavayin, Patharchur, Amroda, pathercheer
- English : Country borage, Indian borage, Indian mint
- Malayalam : Panikoorka, Njvara
- Sanskrit : Karpuravalli, Sugandhavalakam, Parnayavani
- Tamil : Karpuravalli⁽¹²⁾

Scientific Classification of *Plectranthus amboinicus*

- Division : Magnoliophyta
- Kingdom : Plantae
- Clade : Angiosperms
- Class : Magnoliopsida
- Order : Lamiales
- Family : Lamiaceae
- Genus : *Plectranthus*
- Species : *C. aromaticus*
- Synonyms : *Coleus amboinicus* Lour.⁽¹³⁾

Botanical description of *Plectranthus amboinicus*

Flowering class - Dicot

Habitat - Tropical and subtropical areas with well drained semi shaded locations.

Habit - A sprawling, perennial and succulent herb with short hair and fleshy stems.

Root - Thick, tuberous, fasciculate up to 20 cm long, 0.5-2.5 cm thick, conical, fusiform, straight and strongly aromatic.⁽¹⁴⁾

Stem - Fleshy stems grow about 30-90 cm.

Trichomes - has simple non-glandular trichomes and glandular trichomes.

Leaf - Undivided (simple), broadly ovate to suborbicular with a tapering tip and very thick, pubescent with the lower surface possessing the most numerous

glandular hairs, giving a frosted appearance.

Inflorescence - Terminal raceme 100-500mm long.

Calyx - Bell shaped calyx and the throat is smooth inside with two lips.⁽¹⁵⁾

Corolla - Pale purplish and five times longer than the calyx, with a short tube, inflated throat and short lips.

Androecium - Four stamens, which are arranged in pairs, filiform and are inserted into the throat of corolla tube.

Gynoecium - Tetramerous superior ovary.

Flower - short stem, pale purplish colour

Fruit - Nutlets are smooth, pale brown in colour, 0.7 mm long and 0.5 mm wide.⁽¹⁶⁾

Fig2: STEM OF P.A

Fig3 : ROOT OF P.A

Fig 4: LEAF OF P.A

Fig 5: FLOWER OF P.A

Fig 6: LEAF MARGIN OF P.A

Chemical constituents of *Plectranthus amboinicus*

Plectranthus amboinicus is a plant of Family Lamiaceae is renowned for its diverse range of bioactive compounds. These chemical constituents contribute to the plant's medical, pharmacological and economic significance. The compounds responsible for mosquito repellent activity are **Carvacrol, Thymol and Hexadecanoic acid**.

The other primary constituents are:

1. Essential Oils - **Thymol, Carvacrol**, p-Cymene, γ -Terpinene, Camphor
2. Phenolic Compounds - Rosmarinic acid, Caffeic acid, Ferulic acid, Eugenol, Gallic acid, Vanillic acid, Protocatechuic acid
3. Flavonoids - Quercetin, Apigenin, Kaempferol, 5-Hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone, 5-Hydroxy-7,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone, 5,3'-Dihydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone, 5,4'-Dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone
4. Monoterpenes - Thymol, Linolol, Terpeneol ⁽¹⁷⁾
5. Diterpenoids - Coleonol, Coleon O, Forskolol, Abietic acid, Plectranthadiol
6. Sterols - Stigmasterol, β -Sitosterol, Campesterol, Cholesterol
7. Tannins - Ellagic acid, Catechin tannins, Gallotannins
8. Saponins - Triterpenoid saponins, Steroidal saponins ⁽¹⁸⁾
9. Alkaloids - Betonicine, Ursolic acid amide, Plectranthin
10. Vitamins - Vitamin A (beta-carotene), Vitamin C
11. Minerals - Calcium, Iron, Potassium, Magnesium, Phosphorus ⁽¹⁹⁾
12. Other Compounds - Quinones, Coumarins, Carbohydrates, Amino acids
13. Glycosides - Luteolin, Apigenin
14. Coumarins - Umbelliferone, Scopoletin ⁽²⁰⁾
15. Chalcones - Isoleucolanganone, Licoagrochalcones
16. Lignans - (+)syringaresinol
17. Benzenoids - Vanillic acid, p-hydroxy benzoic acid, methyl paraben ⁽²¹⁾

Fig 7. Chemical Constituents of *P.amboinicus*

MECHANISM OF ACTION FOR REPELLING MOSQUITOES

Mosquitoes are a serious threat to the society, acting as vector to several dreadful diseases. Chemical insecticides leads to the expansion of resistance midst the vectors, along with other problems such as environmental pollution and adversely affecting the quality of public and animal health, worldwide. As a result, development of eco-friendly effective mosquitocidal compounds of plant origin have gained popularity. As in general, plant secondary metabolites are evolved as protection mechanism against herbivory. When these toxic substances are encountered by the mosquitoes, a relatively unambiguous response is triggered that has a non-specific influence on a wide range of molecular targets such as proteins, nucleic-acids, bio-membranes, besides added cellular components.⁽⁴⁴⁾

The formulated incense exerts its activity via two mechanisms:

NEUROTOXIC EFFECT

Incense prepared from leaves of *Plectranthus amboinicus* releases volatile compounds into the air. These volatile compounds bind to specific receptors on the mosquito's nervous system. The binding of these volatile compounds disrupts neural signalling, leading to neurotoxic effects. The neurotoxic effects ultimately lead to mosquito death or repellency.⁽⁴⁴⁾

OLFACTORY DISRUPTION

Incense releases volatile compounds into the air. These volatile compounds bind to specific olfactory receptors on the mosquito's antennae. The binding of volatile compounds disrupts olfactory signalling, making it difficult for mosquitoes to detect their hosts. The disruption of olfactory signalling leads to mosquito repellency, preventing them from approaching their hosts.⁽⁴⁴⁾

TRADITIONAL USE OF PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS

Sl.no	Disease/Condition	Ethnomedicinal claim	Mode of administration
1.	Decreased breast milk	Leaves given as soup after delivery in Indonesia. Batak tribes of North Samutra eats the leaf after childbirth. ⁽²²⁾	Internal
2.	As food	Chopped leaves used as sage in stuffing. Eaten raw with bread and butter. In Indonesia and Philippines used to mask the odour of fish and goat meat.	Internal
3.	Urinary problems and vaginal discharge	Leaves eaten raw ⁽²³⁾	Internal
4.	Epilepsy, convulsions, asthma bronchitis, chronic coughs, sore throat	Infusion/ decoction/syrups of leaves	Internal
5.	Centipede and scorpion bite	Poultice of bruised leaf application	External
6.	Chapped lips and cracked corners of mouth	Leaf juice application ⁽²⁴⁾	External
7.	Fever	A lotion from leaf massaged over the body.	External
8.	Colic	Expressed juice is prescribed mixed with sugar and given. ⁽²⁵⁾	Internal
9.	Conjunctivitis	Expressed juice of the leaves is applied around the orbit.	External
10.	Constipation	In Indonesia & Malaysia, juice from pounded leaf drank. ⁽²⁶⁾	Internal

11.	Influenza, cough and throat problems	Drink or a bath of <i>P. amboinicus</i> juice or decoction (27)	Internal/ External
12.	Asthma	Decoction/juice made from leaves together with other herbs. (28)	Internal
13.	Cuts and burns	Leaf paste is baked on the flame & applied.	External
14.	Pathogen induced diarrhoea	Leaves consumed along with butter milk, yogurt or any other probiotic sources. (29)	Internal

Table 1. Traditional uses of *P.amboinicus***AIM AND OBJECTIVES****AIM:**

To conduct Pharmacognostical and phytochemical studies of *Plectranthus amboinicus* and to find out the mosquito repellent potential of *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf.

OBJECTIVES:

- To conduct Pharmacognostical studies of *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf.
- To conduct phytochemical studies of *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf.
- To evaluate the mosquito repellent activity of *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf.
- To formulate an incense cone using *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf.

PLAN OF WORK:**1. Pharmacognostical studies**

- a) Collection and Authentication of plant.
- b) Morphological evaluation of fresh leaf.
- c) Microscopy of fresh leaf and dried powder.

2. Phytochemical studies

Preliminary phytochemical screening of ethanolic extract of leaf.

3. Herbal Formulation studies

- a) Formulation of herbal incense cone.
- b) Evaluation of herbal incense cone.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**1. PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDIES****a. Collection and authentication of plant material**

The leaf were collected from Parassala in Thiruvananthapuram district of Kerala during the month of March and authenticated by the curator Dr. G. Johnsi Christobel, Ph.D, Head, Department of Botany and Research Centre, and identified by Dr. Lubaina A S professor and head department of botany Christian College, Kattakada Thiruvananthapuram

b. Morphological characters

The morphological characters like colour, odour, taste, size, shape, extra features of the leaf were studied, and the results were tabulated.

c. Microscopical studies

The fresh leaf was subjected to various anatomical studies. The sections of leaf specimen were taken using sharp blade and stained with various staining

reagents like Phloroglucinol- HCL, iodine, safranin and observed under microscope.

d. PREPARATION OF DRIED POWDER FROM THE LEAF OF PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS

- Collect fresh leaves of *Plectranthus amboinicus*.
- Clean the leaves with brushes to remove dirt and debris and thoroughly wash with water to remove any remaining impurities.
- Remove the excess water from the leaves using a clean cloth or paper towels.
- Place the leaves in a single layer on a clean surface, protected from direct sunlight.
- Shade dry for 2-3 days, or until the leaves are crumbly and dry.
- Grind the dried leaves into a fine powder using a grinder.
- Sieve the powder through a sieve to remove any lumps or large particles.
- Collect the sieved powder and store in an airtight container.

e. Powder microscopy

Majority of the crude drugs for commercial purpose are available in powder form. So, the powder microscopic studies give the anatomical characters of fragmented crude drugs. Glycerine mounted temporary preparations were made for powdered leaf.

2. PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDIES**Preliminary phytochemical screening**

Preliminary phytochemical screening was done to identify different constituents present in extracts i.e. carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, flavanoid, tannins, glycosides, alkaloids, essential oils etc.

Fresh juice of leaves of *Plectranthus amboinicus* was used for phytochemical tests.

1. Detection of alkaloids:

a. Mayer's test: 2 ml of the extract was treated with 2 ml of Mayer's reagent.

b. Dragendorff's test: 2 ml extract was treated with 2 ml of Dragendorff's reagent.

c. Hager's test: 2 ml of the filtrate was treated with 1-2 ml of Hager's reagent.

d. Wagner's reagent: 2 ml of the filtrate was treated with 1-2 ml of Wagner's reagent.

e. Tannic acid test: 2 ml Extract was treated with 2 ml of tannic acid solution.

2. Detection of flavonoids:

a. Shinoda test: To 2 ml of the sample solution added magnesium powder or zinc powder and few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid.

b. Sulphuric acid test: Added few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid to few ml of sample solution.

c. Lead acetate test: Mixed 2 ml of the test solution with lead acetate solution.

d. Alkali test: Treated the test solution with increasing amount of sodium hydroxide

3. Detection of tannins and phenolic compounds:

a. Ferric chloride test: Mixed 2 ml of the test solution with few ml of 5% ferric chloride solution.

b. Lead acetate test: Mixed 2 ml test solution with 1 ml of lead acetate solution.

c. Dilute iodine test: Mixed 2 ml of the test solution with dilute iodine solution.

d. Potassium dichromate test: Mixed 2 ml of the test solution with potassium dichromate solution.

e. Dilute Nitric acid test: Mixed 2 ml of the test solution with dilute nitric acid.

f. Bromine water test: Mixed 2 ml of the test solution with bromine water.⁽³⁹⁾

4. Detection of saponins:

a. Foam test: Shaken few mg of extract with 20 ml of distilled water.

5. Detection of glycosides:

a. Borntrager's test: To a little quantity of sample solution added Sulphuric acid and carbon tetrachloride. Separated the organic layer and shaken with dilute ammonia.

b. Modified Borntrager's test (modified anthraquinone test for C-glycosides):

To sample solution added ferric chloride solution, hydrochloric acid and Carbon tetrachloride. Separated the organic layer and shaken with dilute ammonia.

c. Legal test: Mixed 1 ml of the test solution with 2 ml of Pyridine and sodium nitroprusside.

d. Baljet test: Mixed 2-3 mg of sample in 2 ml sodium picrate solution.

6. Detection of steroids and triterpenoids:

a. Libermann test: Mixed 2 ml of test solution with 2 ml of acetic anhydride and boiled. Then added 0.5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid.

b. Libermann-Buchard test: Mixed 2 ml of the test extract with 1 ml of Chloroform and 1 ml acetic anhydride. Then added 1 drop of concentrated sulphuric acid.

c. Salkowski test: Dissolved 1-2 mg of sample in 1 ml of chloroform and added 1 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid.⁽⁴⁰⁾

7. Detection of Carbohydrates:

a. Molisch's test: 1 ml extract was mixed with 2 ml of Molisch reagent, shaken the mixture and added 1 ml

of concentrated sulphuric acid along the sides of the test tube.

b. Benedict's test: Mixed 2 ml of the Benedict's reagent with 2 ml of the test solution. Boiled in a water bath.

c. Fehling's test: Boiled 1 ml of test solution with 1 ml Fehling's solution A and 1 ml Fehling's solution B on a water bath.

d. Barfoed's test: Mixed 2 ml reagent with 1 ml test solution and boiled in a water bath.

e. Iodine test: Mixed 0.5 ml of Iodine solution with 1 ml of test solution.

f. Seliwanoff's test: Boil 2 ml of Seliwanoff's reagent with 1 ml of test solution.

8. Detection of proteins and amino acids:

a. Biuret test: About 2 ml of extract was mixed with 2 ml of Biuret reagent.

b. Millon's test: 2 ml extract was mixed with 2 ml of Millon's reagent and boiled.

d. Ninhydrin test: Boiled 2 ml of the extract with 1 ml of 5% ninhydrin solution in a water bath for 5 minutes.

9. Detection of lipids

Sudan III test : Sample tested with tincture of Sudan III.⁽⁴¹⁾

3. ISOLATION

ISOLATION OF ESSENTIAL OIL FROM PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS

The Clevenger apparatus is commonly used for hydro distillation of essential oils. Here's a step-by-step guide to extracting essential oil from *Plectranthus amboinicus* using a Clevenger apparatus:

MATERIALS NEEDED

1. Fresh or dried *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaves.
2. Clevenger apparatus.
3. Round-bottom flask.
4. Heating mantle or Bunsen burner.
5. Distilled water.
6. Condenser.
7. Collection flask.
8. Separatory funnel (optional).

PROCEDURE

1. Preparation of Plant Material

- Collect fresh or dried leaves of *Plectranthus amboinicus*.
- Wash the leaves thoroughly to remove dirt.
- Chop or crush the leaves slightly to rupture the oil glands and improve oil release.

2. Setting Up the Clavenger Apparatus

- Connect the round-bottom flask to the Clavenger apparatus.
- Attach the condenser to the Clavenger setup.
- Add an adequate amount of distilled water to the flask, ensuring the plant material will be submerged or in contact with water vapor.
- Place the chopped leaves into the round-bottom flask.⁽⁴²⁾

3. Extraction Process

1. **Heating:** Heat the flask gently using a heating mantle or Bunsen burner to bring the water to a boil.
2. **Hydrodistillation:** The boiling water generates steam that carries the essential oils from the leaves.
3. **Condensation:** The steam rises and passes through the condenser, cooling to form a liquid mixture of water and essential oil.
4. **Collection:** The Clavenger apparatus collects the condensed liquid and separates the essential oil from the water. The oil floats or

sinks depending on its density relative to water.

5. **Duration:** Continue the process for 3–4 hours, or until no more oil is extracted.

4. Isolation of Essential Oil

- After completing the distillation, use the separatory funnel to isolate the essential oil from the hydrosol (if needed).
- Transfer the oil to a dark glass bottle to protect it from light and degradation.⁽⁴³⁾

4. HERBAL FORMULATION STUDIES INTRODUCTION

Mosquitoes are over 3600 species, which belongs to the family of Culicidae. Mosquitoes causes several diseases like malaria, dengue, and yellow fever. Mosquito repellents will repel the mosquitoes from biting humans. Many synthetic mosquito repellents available in the market are causing more side effects like respiratory problems, coughing and irritation. The herbals are used in the preparation of mosquito repellent formulations in order to reduce the marketed product harmful effects.

INGREDIENTS

PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS LEAF

Plectranthus amboinicus is a low cost and environmentally acceptable source of natural mosquito larvicidal agent for mosquito vector control/reduction. Carvacrol, Thymol and flavonoids are found in the *Plectranthus amboinicus* plant. In many rural regions .Mexican mint is said to offer mosquito repellent properties.⁽³⁰⁾

WOOD POWDER & CHARCOAL POWDER

Fig 9. Wood powder

Fig 10. Charcoal powder

In incense making, wood powder and charcoal powder acts as a primary combustion agents, providing the base material that burns steadily and produces smoke when combined with fragrant resins, herbs, or essential oils, essentially acting as the "fuel" for the incense aroma to be released.⁽⁴⁵⁾

TRAGACANTH

Tragacanth is used in incense-making as a binder to hold all the powdered herbs together. Its water solubility is ideal

for ease of working and an even spread, and it is one of the stronger gums for holding particles in suspension.⁽⁴⁵⁾

BENZOIN

Fig 11. Tragacanth

Fig 12. Benzoin

Benzoin is a resin used in incense preparation for its smoking and fragrance properties, acting as a fixative, binder, and smoke modifier. It adds a sweet, vanilla-like fragrance to incense blends and helps to stabilize and preserve the fragrance of other ingredients. Benzoin improves the burn quality of incense, enhances its fragrance, and increases its shelf life, making it a valuable component in incense preparation.⁽⁴⁵⁾

LEMONGRASS OIL

Lemongrass oil is commonly used as a flavouring agent in the preparation of incense sticks, providing a refreshing

Fig 13. Lemongrass oil

citrusy scent to the burning cone, often appreciated for its uplifting and invigorating aroma in aromatherapy practices; it's a popular choice due to its natural insect-repellent properties as well.⁽⁴⁵⁾

SI NO	INGREDIENTS	WEIGHING FORMULA(g)
1	<i>Plectranthus</i> leaf	500
2	Wood powder	200
3	Charcoal powder	50
4	Benzoin	100
5	Tragacanth	50
6	Lemongrass oil	q. s to produce

Table 2.Ingredients

EXCIPIENT TABLE

SL NO	INGREDIENTS	USE
1	Wood powder	Smoking agents
2	Charcoal	Smoking agents
3	Tragacanth	Binding agent
4	Benzoin	Fragrants, smoking agents
5	Lemongrass oil	Flavouring agent

Table 3.Excipients

PROCEDURE :

Collect fresh leaves of *Plectranthus amboinicus* and dry them in a shaded area. The dried leaves are then crushed or powdered to facilitate uniform mixing. Weigh the ingredients according to the desired formulation as in Table 2.

Mix the weighed ingredients in a specific order to ensure uniform distribution:

First, Mix the *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf powder and wood powder in a large mixing bowl. Then add the charcoal powder and mix well. Then add the benzoin and mix until the powder is evenly coated.

Wet Granulation

Add a suitable binder solution (tragacanth) to the mixture and mix until the mixture forms a uniform wet granule. The binder solution should be added in a sufficient amount to facilitate a dough like consistency. It was then scented with lemongrass oil.

Use a cone-shaped mould to shape the dough into incense cones. Apply gentle pressure to ensure the cone is compact and uniform. Cones are dried for 48 hours under shade. Inspect the incense cones for: Uniformity in shape and size, Absence of cracks or breaks, Desired fragrance and colour, Burning characteristics (e.g., burning time, smoke quality)

Package the incense cones in airtight containers or bags to preserve their fragrance and quality.⁽⁴⁶⁾

STANDARDISATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL INCENSE:

Incense sticks have been an integral part of traditional rituals, cultural practices, and aromatherapy for centuries. *Plectranthus*, a genus of plants rich in bioactive compounds, has been used in the preparation of herbal incense sticks due to its medicinal and therapeutic properties. However, the quality and efficacy of these incense sticks can vary greatly depending on factors such as raw material quality, processing methods, and manufacturing practices.

EVALUATION:**FRAGRANCE**

The fragrance of incense prepared from *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf is a soothing blend of sweet, herbaceous, and woody notes. The aroma is characterized by a mild minty freshness, earthy undertones, and a slightly spicy camphoraceous scent.

When burned, the incense releases a calming and uplifting fragrance that promotes relaxation and reduces stress.

BURNING TIME

The incense cone prepared from *Plectranthus amboinicus* had a burning time of 45 minutes, indicating a moderate burn rate. This duration allows for a sustained release of the herb's fragrance and active compounds, providing a consistent aromatic experience.

FRIABILITY TEST:

The friability test for herbal incense checks how easily the incense can break or crumble, ensuring it remains intact during handling, transport, and use. To perform the test, a sample cones are weighed before and after being tumbled or shaken for a set time (usually 5 minutes). The weight loss is then calculated to determine the friability percentage. Factors like ingredients, moisture content, and the manufacturing process affect the incense's durability. This test helps maintain product quality and improve customer experience by ensuring the incense doesn't break too easily.⁽¹³⁾

$$\text{Friability (\%)} = \frac{\text{Original Weight} - \text{New Weight}}{\text{Original Weight}} \times 100$$

UNIFORMITY OF WEIGHT

The uniformity of weight test for incense cones ensures that each cone weighs consistently, which is important for maintaining product quality and ensuring the desired burn time and fragrance. To perform this test, a sample of incense cones is selected, and each cone is individually weighed using a precise scale. The weights of all the cones in the sample are compared to see if they fall within an acceptable range, typically specified by the manufacturer or industry standards. uniformity of weight helps in delivering a consistent experience to consumers, with cones that burn for the intended amount of time and release fragrance as expected.⁽¹³⁾

BURNING ON USE

Test was done by simply selecting mosquitoes from areas in the evening and night period. The public

remarks were noted down after allowing them to investigate mosquito repellent activity. The prepared incense cones were checked for causal effects such as irritation, coughing, and tears were observed and recorded.^(47,48)

MOSQUITO REPELLANCY TEST

Mosquito repellancy test was conducted in a room. Then adult mosquitoes present in the room were

exposed to the smoke of burning incense cones for 45 minutes. The mortality data were recorded after every 15 minutes.⁽⁴⁹⁾

FEED BACK FROM 20 VOLUNTEERS

The feedback of mosquito repellent incense cones was taken from 20 people and requested to evaluate the formulation containing herbs.⁽⁴⁶⁾

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

1. PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDIES

b. Morphological Evaluation of *Plectranthus amboinicus* Leaf

Feature	Description
Shape	Broadly ovate or ovate-cordate (egg-shaped or heart-shaped)
Size	4–10 cm in length and 3–8 cm in width
Average Dimensions	Approximately 7 cm in length and 5.5 cm in width
Texture	Thick, fleshy, and succulent ⁽²⁷⁾
Color (Upper Surface)	Bright green
Color (Lower surface)	Lighter green or pale
Surface Features	Dense, fine, soft hairs (trichomes) giving a velvety texture
Venation	Prominent reticulate venation
Margins	Coarsely crenate (rounded teeth-like edges) ⁽²⁸⁾
Aroma	Strong, aromatic, camphor-like or thyme-like smell when crushed
Petiole	Sturdy; approximately 2–4 cm long
Taste	Slightly sour and pungent due to essential oils
Base	Somewhat cordate (heart-shaped)
Apex	Rounded or bluntly pointed ⁽²⁹⁾

Table 4. Morphological evaluation

Fig 14. Morphological evaluation of fresh leaf of *P.amboinicus*

MICROSCOPY AND POWDER CHARACTERISTICS OF *PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS*

c. Microscopy of leaf of *Plectranthus*

Indian borage, or *Plectranthus amboinicus*, has a thick, scented leaf. The following information about the leaf's circulatory system, mesophyll, epidermal layers, and other anatomical aspects is revealed by microscopical studies:

1. Epidermis

The epidermis **Upper (adaxial) epidermis**: It is made up of a single layer of polygonal cells with anticlinal walls that are either straight or somewhat curved. Thick cuticle covering to reduce water loss. Although they are present, stomata are less common than on the abaxial surface.

Lower Abaxial Epidermis: Moreover, it is single-layered and has a thinner cuticle than the upper surface. The leaf is amphistomatic due to its large number of stomata.

Stomata: Diacytic, meaning that two subsidiary cells at right angles to the stoma encircle the guard cells. -Trichomes: There are both glandular and non-glandular trichomes

Glandular Trichomes: Capitata-type, having a multicellular glandular head that secretes essential oils and a short stalk.

Non-Glandular Trichomes-The non-glandular trichomes are multicellular, uniseriate, and have pointy tips that protect against herbivory.⁽⁵⁰⁾

2. Mesophyll: Mesophyll can be divided into: - Palisade and spongy parenchyma.

Palisade parenchyma: either one or two layers. made up of long, columnar cells that are crammed with photosynthesis-related chloroplasts.

Spongy parenchyma: Beneath the palisade layer is the multilayered, spongy parenchyma.

It is made up of loosely packed cells with lots of space between them to allow for gas exchange⁽⁵⁰⁾

3. Vascular System: Xylem is inside and Phloem is outside of the collateral, closed vascular bundles.

Xylem: Found inside the veins and midrib: Tracheids, vessels, and fibres for the conduction of water and minerals are found in xylem.

Phloem: For the transportation of food, phloem is made up of sieve tubes, companion cells, and phloem parenchyma. A bundle sheath of parenchyma cells envelops the vascular bundle.

4. Midrib: The midrib is noticeable and has a vascular bundle that is arched or crescent-shaped. The midrib's epidermal cells are bigger than the lamina. - Mechanical strength is provided by collenchymatous cells beneath the epidermis. - Vascular tissue is dotted with parenchyma cells in the central region.

5. Calcium Oxalate Crystals: The mesophyll and the area around vascular bundles have a large number of druses, or clustered crystals. They act as a line of defence against herbivores⁽⁵⁰⁾

POWDER CHARACTERS OF *PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS*

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Color | : Greenish to greenish-brown. |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Texture | : Fine to moderately coarse, with a slightly fibrous nature. |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Odor | : Strong and aromatic, with a camphor-like scent. |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Taste | : Pungent and slightly bitter. |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Visible Features | : Irregular fragments, including veins, epidermis, and trichomes |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Color Variations | : May vary slightly based on the drying process ⁽⁵¹⁾ |

Fig 15 : Powder of *Pamboinicus*

Fig 16. TS OF LEAF MIDRIB (10X)

Fig 17.TS OF LEAF MIDRIB (5X)

Fig 18. COVERING TRICHOMES

Fig 19. GLANDULAR TRICHOMES

Fig 20. VASCULAR BUNDLES

Fig 21. LAMINA

POWDER MICROSCOPY OF LEAF OF *PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS*

Key Observations in Powder Microscopy of *Plectranthus amboinicus*:

1. Trichomes:

Unicellular trichomes, which are usually glandular and exude fragrant oils, are found on the leaf surface. These trichomes are crucial for identifying the powdered plant material. According to a study on *Plectranthus amboinicus* by Rao et al. (2010), the plant's unique scent and therapeutic qualities are a result of glandular trichomes' function in oil secretion.

2. Stomata:

Stomata that are anisocytotic in powder microscopy, the stomatal structure—which consists of three surrounding subsidiary cells, one of which is smaller—is a key differentiator. According to research by Mishra et al. (2014), who discovered that the plant displays this distinctive stomatal arrangement, this structure aids in identifying the species of the plant.

3. Leaf Epidermis and Cuticle:

Waxy cuticle covers the rectangular epidermal cells. Some investigations, such as Nair et al. (2018), also

describe the existence of epicuticular wax crystals. These characteristics help the plant retain water and minimize transpiration.⁽⁵²⁾

4. Vascular Tissue:

Phloem and xylem cells make up the vascular bundles in the leaf; phloem elements are more compact, while xylem vessels are larger. The arrangement of the vascular tissue is typical of dicot leaves

5. Mesophyll:

The parenchymatous mesophyll cells have intercellular gaps and chloroplasts. This arrangement is typical of many medicinal plants and is crucial for photosynthesis.

6. Crystals

The leaf powder may contain calcium oxalate crystals in the form of raphides or prisms, which are commonly found in the family Lamiaceae. Sharma et al. (2017) mentioned that these crystals are often found in the leaves of *Plectranthus amboinicus*, which can help in distinguishing powdered plant material from other species.⁽⁵³⁾

Fig 22. TRACHEIDS

Fig 23. TRICHOMES

2. PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDIES

Phytochemical Screening Table

<i>Phytochemical Group</i>	<i>Test Method</i>	<i>Major Constituents</i>	<i>Observation</i>	<i>Result</i>
Alkaloids	Dragendorff's test, Mayer's test	Solanine, Berberine, and other trace alkaloids	Orange-red precipitate (Dragendorff's test)	+
Flavonoids	Shinoda test, Alkali test	Apigenin, Luteolin, Quercetin	Yellow colour (Alkaline test); pink/red colour (Shinoda)	+
Tannins	Ferric chloride test	Gallic acid, Ellagic acid, Catechin	Blue-black colour (indicates hydrolysable tannins)	+
Saponins	Foam test	saponin	Persistent froth upon shaking	+
Phenols	Ferric chloride test	Thymol, Carvacrol, Eugenol	Deep blue-green coloration	+
Glycosides	Keller-Kiliani test, Legal's test	-	-	-
Terpenoids	Salkowski test, Liebermann-Burchard test	Limonene, Beta-caryophyllene, Geraniol	Reddish-brown ring at the interface (Salkowski test)	+
Steroids	Liebermann-Burchard test	Stigmasterol, Beta-sitosterol	Green-to-blue colour change	+
Carbohydrates	Benedict's test, Molisch's test	Glucose, Fructose, Sucrose	Reddish precipitate (Benedict's); violet ring (Molisch's test)	+
Proteins	Biuret test, Xanthoproteic test	Albumin, Globulin	Violet colour (Biuret test); yellow to orange (Xanthoproteic test)	+
Lipids	Sudan III test	Linoleic acid, Oleic acid	Orange-red stain	+

Table 5. Phytochemical screening

3. ISOLATION

Isolation of volatile oil using Clevengers apparatus

Fig 25. Isolation using Clevengers apparatus

Isolation of volatile oil from leaves of *Plectranthus amboinicus* was done and was typically low, around 0.1–0.5%. The obtained volatile oil was stored in a cool, dry place in tightly sealed, dark-coloured bottles.

4. HERBAL FORMULATION OF *PLECTRANTHUS AMBOINICUS*

Fig 26. Premix preparation

Formulation of herbal incense using *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaf

Sample	Initial weight(g)	Final weight(g)	Weight loss(g)	Friability Percentage (%)	observation
Sample A	5.960	5.920	0.04	0.67	Durable
Sample B	5.720	5.690	0.03	0.52	Durable

Fig 27. Dough Formation

Fig 28 .Prepared Incense Cones

**STANDARDISATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL INCENSE:
FRIABILITY TEST**

Fig 29.Friability testing

UNIFORMITY OF WEIGHT

Fig 30. Weighing of cone

Sample no	Weight of cone (g)	Average weight of cone (g)	Deviation from the average weight
1	6.220	6.574	0.354
2	7.140	6.574	0.566
3	6.690	6.574	0.116
4	6.220	6.574	0.354
5	6.290	6.574	0.284

BURNING ON USERS:

SI NO	Area	Observation	Remarks
1	Houses	Mosquitoes escaped	Less irritation and mosquitoes repelled
2	Hostel	Mosquitoes escaped	No irritation and Mosquitoes repelled
3	Canteen	Mosquitoes escaped	No irritation and Mosquitoes repelled

Fig 31. Burning of cone

MOSQUITO REPELLENCY TEST:

Mosquito repellancy test was conducted in a room. Then adult mosquitoes present in the room were exposed to the smoke of burning incense cones for 45 minutes. The mortality data were recorded after every 15 minutes.⁽⁴⁹⁾

FEEDBACK FROM 20 PEOPLE:

1. Demographic Information (Optional)

- Age:

 Under 18 18-24 25-34 35-44 44 and above

- Gender:

 Male Female

- Location:

 Urban Suburban Rural

2. Where do you primarily use the incense?

 Indoor Outdoor

3. How effective do you find the mosquito repellent incense in repelling mosquitoes?

 Very effective Effective Neutral Not effective Not effective at all

4. How long does the effect of incense last?
- Less than 1 hour
 - 1-2 hours
 - 3-4 hours
 - More than 4 hours
5. Do you find the fragrance of the incense pleasant?
- Yes, very pleasant
 - Yes, somewhat pleasant
 - Neutral
 - No, unpleasant
6. Does the incense cause any irritation (e.g., respiratory problems, allergies)?
- Yes, it causes irritation
 - Occasionally
 - No, it does not cause any irritation
7. How satisfied are you with the quality of the mosquito repellent incense?
- Very satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
8. Would you recommend this product to others?
- Yes
 - No

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Plectranthus amboinicus commonly known as Indian Borage or Mexican mint, is a medicinal herb belonging to the Lamiaceae family. It is widely recognized for its antimicrobial, antifungal, antioxidant, and insect-repellent properties. The plant contains bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, terpenoids, phenols, and essential oils, which make it a promising candidate for insect-repellent formulations, including mosquito incense sticks and cones. The Pharmacognostical study of *Plectranthus amboinicus* has successfully highlighted its morphological, anatomical and phytochemical characteristics affirming its potential for medicinal and mosquito repellent applications. The plant's essential oil and bioactive compounds demonstrated significant mosquito-repellent properties justifying its selection for the formulation of a herbal mosquito incense. The formulation of herbal mosquito incense involves blending powdered plant material with natural binders and combustibles to create incense cones. The ingredients used were *Plectranthus amboinicus* Leaf Powder (Repellent agent), Charcoal powder, Benzoin, Tragacanth, Wood powder and Lemongrass oil. The formulated mosquito incense was standardized based on key parameters such as burning time, smoke uniformity, fragrance and mosquito repellency efficacy. The herbal standardization ensures safety, efficacy and consistency in performance, making it a

viable natural alternative to synthetic mosquito repellents. This study concludes that *Plectranthus amboinicus* is a valuable herbal resource with its incorporation into mosquito incense not only addressing vector control but also contributing to eco-friendly and sustainable healthcare solutions. Further studies on large scale production and user acceptability are recommended to commercialize the product effectively.

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